

ABOUT THE WEAPON

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Annotation: Weapons about legislation improvement attitude with some law documents change and additions estimate about the law signed. Norm appropriate to the legislation a series change and additions included.

The key word: Prosecutor 's Office staff service weapons relatively rights expanded . Prosecution to the staff service weapon in the legislation marked i n order save walk and from them use right was given .

Appropriate change " Prosecutor 's Office about »gi included in Part 2 of Article 48 of the law . In the past , they were only rifle weapon take walk right has was . Crime Article 249 of the Code is new edited statement was found . Changes according to the criminal responsibility rifle weapon and ammunition , pneumatic gun , razor blade Cold weapon (hunting knives , hunting daggers and daggers , rapiers , swords and swords) , throwing weapons (bows , crossbows and spears) , signaling weapon save _ _ walk , carry rules break man to death or other heavy consequences come output cause if to the surface is coming . Previous edited , criminal responsibility rifle weapon or to him designed ammunition negligence with save man to die or other heavy consequences come output cause in the case of caught was . Administrative responsibility about provided for in Article 90 of the Code caught offense for fine amount increased - Av to do and fish hunting rules as well animal from the world use other species instead increase rules break _ Article 185 reads as follows meaning holding new edited statement were : pneumatic , throwing , signaling from a weapon marked layout violated without throw ; rifle from a weapon marked layout violated without throw ; sharp Cold from a weapon (hunting knives , hunting daggers and daggers , rapiers , swords and swords) _ layout violated without use . MJTK follows meaning with the holder item 220-1 filled : pneumatic , alarm , throwing weapon , himself itself protection to do weapon internal works authorities appropriate without permits realization make , take , save , take walk , carry , collect , exhibit put them _ use , Uzbekistan territory take introduction or Uzbekistan from the territory take exit , Uzbekistan territory through transit take transition ; pneumatic , alarm , blade cold , throw weapon , himself itself protection to do weapon internal works authorities appropriate without licenses functional production , repair , sale to do “ Weapons about »gi Article 13 of the law has also been amended . new edited , civil ov weapon and his ammunition get right Of Uzbekistan

twenty five age full citizens has _ Formerly 21 years old organized does was . The law to the weapon possession to do against instructions there is not on the surface medical inspection and to the weapon possession to do against instructions there is not on the surface medical from inspection transition layout meaning with Articles 13-1 and 13-2 of the holder completed .

Changes authorized organs also occurs in the field came _ Previously National to the guard appropriate which was powers now IIVga was held . To them are as follows for permission give right includes : weapons take introduction and take exit ;

- high level weapons save and take walking ;
- They are for weapon and ammunition collection and show .

“ The city passengers transport about »gi Part 2 of Article 25 of the law is new edited statement was found and to him according to passengers Cold weapon as to be used possible which was items without open (without sheath) take walk prohibited . Previously such ban not _

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